

Predictive Analytics for Marketing Campaign Outcomes Using Supervised Machine Learning Algorithms

Blessington Naveen Palaparathi
*Department of Computer Science and Engineering
 Acharya Nagarjuna University, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India*

Dr. S. Akthar
*Department of Computer Science
 Govt.College for Women, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India*

Abstract- As data availability grows, putting it to proper use and generating valuable insights to create strategies and action plans could make businesses thrive. While business analytics has been there around serving this purpose, the novel predictive analytics augmented with machine learning provides cutting edge capabilities. Predictive analytics has proven contribution in analyzing customer behaviors, football game outcomes, medical diagnosis, fraud detection, insurance, customer retention and many other fields. Since multiple algorithms are available, it is a challenging task to pick the correct model for a given dataset. In this study, we develop and compare machine learning models to predict if a customer will participate in a term deposit scheme using data from a bank marketing campaign. LR, SVM, NBC and QDA classification models are implemented. Key performance indicators such as precision, accuracy, recall, F-measure, and ROC-AUC are used to evaluate the capability of each model. Based on the results generated, the study concludes that QDA algorithm outperformed other models.

Keywords: Predictive analytics, Machine Learning Algorithms, Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, K Nearest Neighbor, SVM, Naïve Bayes, Gaussian NB Bayes, Gradient Boosting, Random Forest, MLP Classifier, Ada Boost, Quadratic Discriminant Analysis.

Abbreviations: PA - Predictive Analytics, LR - Logistic Regression, SVM - Support Vector Machine, NB - Naïve Bayes and QDA - Quadratic Discriminant Analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is a natural human trait to anticipate or predict future events with a certain degree of accuracy, based on past experiences. Predictive Analytics processes present and past data to forecast future opportunities or anticipate problems before they occur. While traditional BI technologies are dependent on user input to discover patterns reflecting deductive behavior, PA offers an inductive approach allowing the data to present itself. This involves principles of statistics, machine learning, neural computing, computational mathematics, and artificial intelligence [1-2]. Many industry verticals like Digital Marketing, Banking and Finance, Health care and Medicine, Entertainment, social media, Education etc., adopted it. Machine learning rummages through huge volumes of data to generate actionable insights leading to the development of a robust PA architecture eliminating the drawbacks of the traditional methods [3]. Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, KNN, SVM, Decision Tree, Random Forest, XGBoost and Ada Boost are popular and widely used algorithms [4,5]. Whereas Ridge, Quadratic Discriminant Analysis, Linear Discriminant Analysis, Extra Trees Classifier, Extreme Gradient Boosting, Light Gradient Boosting Machine, and Dummy Classifier are considered advanced automated machine learning (AutoML) techniques [5]. Both classification and regression models support prediction on different kinds of data, however their usage primarily depends on the nature of the dataset. This study aims at demonstrating the efficacy of some of the popular and advanced classification models to predict whether a customer will make a term deposit using a marketing campaign dataset.

II. RELATED WORK

The application of PA is rapidly emerging across various industries with an estimated market share of \$22 billion and projected to reach \$100 billion by 2034. In [1], authors presented opportunities and challenges of predictive analytics to develop efficient marketing strategies, segmenting targeted consumers and to analyse social media. The authors in [3] implemented three popular ML methods like NB, KNN and SVM for predictive analytics on credit card dataset and their results concluded that SVM outperformed other algorithms in terms of accuracy and precision. [4] carried out experiments using Decision Tree (J48), RF, SVM, and LR machine learning models to predict student's final grade, which would assist educators to improve student success. The findings revealed that J48 as the best predictive analytics model with the highest prediction accuracy rate of 99.6%. In [5] intraoperative predictive analytics is performed to predict post-induction hypotension using eight machine learning techniques on existing electronic health record data. The GB machine model demonstrated strong discrimination in both training and

testing. Authors in [6] performed a comparative study of PA using ML techniques to predict football match outcomes. Their study concluded that AutoML models, especially logistic regression, offered better predictive accuracy than traditional manual methods like Random Forest, XGBoost, SVM, and AdaBoost. In [7], authors used DT and LR models to forecast the NFL game outcomes. The results indicated that the decision tree model predicted win-loss with up to 79% accuracy and the binary logistic regression model predicted outcomes or win-loss with up to 83% accuracy. [8] presented results of implementing artificial neural networks to investigate customer behavior regarding bank deposits and results highlighted that neural networks have a good discriminatory power than the traditional discriminant analysis. In [9], to predict the performance of salespeople authors applied a Naive Bayes model and assessed the performance of with a confusion matrix and other techniques to achieve results that showed an accuracy of 92.50% for the whole model. In [10], Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and SVN are developed to predict the customers' behavior regarding restaurant preference. The results indicated that ANN provided 93.13 average accuracy across analyzed customers compared to only 54.00% for SVM with a sigmoid kernel function. Authors in [11] used machine-learning techniques such as decision tree, cluster analysis and Naive Bayes algorithm to analyze customer characteristics and attributes with historical purchase records to identify key factors that affect potential purchase behavior. The results indicated that the prediction effect of decision tree is better than clustering analysis and Naive Bayesian algorithm. The authors in [12] developed a diagnosis system and implemented four prediction models (RF, SVM, NB, and DT) to predict diabetes and found that the SVM algorithm performed with an accuracy of 83.1%. In [13], linear QDA was successfully implemented to detect heart disease. Table.1 below shows the comparison of the predictive models implemented on different datasets and the results achieved thereof.

Table-1 Model Comparison Table

Approach	Case Study	Models Evaluated	Best Results	Accuracy
Theng, D et al (2020) [3]	Credit Card dataset	KNN, NB, SVM	SVM	NA
Bujang, et al (2021) [4]	Student Final Grade	DT(J48), LR, RF, SVM	DT(J48)	99.6%
Kendale et al (2018) [5]	Post-induction hypotension	ANN, GBM, KNN, LDA, LR, NB, RF, SVM	GBM	NA
Rezaul et al (2025) [6]	Football match outcomes	Ada, KNN, LR, NB, RF, SVM, XGB	LR	70%
Gifford et al (2023) [7]	NFL Game outcomes	DT, LR	LR	83%
Badea et al (2014) [8]	Customer bank deposit behavior	ANN, Discriminant Analysis	ANN	NA
Calixto et al (2020) [9]	Salespeople performance	NB	NB	92.5%
Zheng et al (2013) [10]	Customer Restaurant preference	ANN, SVN	ANN	93.13%
Li et al (2019) [11]	Customer Purchase behavior	Cluster Analysis, DT and NB	DT	NA
Edeh et al (2022) [12]	Diabetes prediction	DT, NB, RF, SVM	SVM	83.1%
Saikumar et al (2022) [13]	Heart Disease Detection	Linear QDA	QDA	96%

From the literature reviewed so far, each model appears to perform better than others depending on the dataset and specific parameter tuning. This study aims to implement and compare multiple machine learning models using a high-quality publicly available direct marketing campaign dataset.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY AND ALGORITHM

The proposed work, therefore, implements machine learning models to predict whether a customer will make a term deposit. As depicted in Figure 1 below, the proposed work and methodology involve four major stages such as data

collection, analysis, model development and evaluation. Each of these stages is elaborated more in the following sections.

Figure 1. Diagram of Methodology

3.1 Data Collection

The dataset used for this purpose is from UCI Machine Learning Repository [14], a reputed collection of databases used by machine learning community. The data is related to direct telemarketing campaigns of a Portuguese banking institution. The marketing campaigns were based on phone calls often requiring more than one call to the same client to assess if the product (bank term deposit) would be ('yes') or ('no'). The dataset is a multivariate in nature with 41188 record samples, 20 inputs and total of 16 features.

3.2 Data Analysis

Exploratory data analysis was conducted on the collected raw dataset to fix anomalies such as null values, outliers, ordinal and feature encoding, standardizing the numerical values. The data is then further processed for transformations and feature selection to generate the training and test dataset to be as input (80:20) for the machine learning models. Preparing the training set is an important step as it is the key to developing a reliable predictive analytical model.

3.3 Model Development

The following machine-learning algorithms were trained: logistic regression, support vector machines, Naïve Bayes and Quadratic Discriminant Analysis. Although the goal was to develop a predictive model, an additional aim was to explore how various machine-learning algorithms compare. All available features after recursive feature elimination were used for all training algorithms.

3.3.1 Logistic Regression

It is a supervised machine-learning algorithm also referred to as a linear classifier. It mainly applies to usecases where the outcome is a yes (1) or no (0), reflecting the binary behavior of the algorithm. This classifier is known to be simple and fast but exhibits poor performance when the data is non-linear in structure. In [6,7], LR is used to develop a predictive model for football games, and the authors could establish a successful case of predicting the game outcomes. The formula to implement LR is as shown below in Eqn. (1), where the probability that $y=1$, with x input variables:

$$P(y = 1 | x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(w^T x + b)}} \tag{1}$$

$P(y=1|x)$ is the probability for a positive event ($y=1$) to occur; x is the vector of features (independent variables); y = predicted output; b is the bias term, w is the weight vector, e is the base of natural logarithm.

3.3.2 Support Vector Machines

It is a margin-based classifier and supervised machine-learning model that is effective in high dimensional data. In [3, 12], SVM is used to construct a predictive model for credit card approval and diabetes diagnosis and achieved great accuracy. In [15] authors discovered a novel approach to SVM with Pearson VII function having used multiple kernel approaches, like sigmoid, linear, polynomial, radial, and Pearson, which is a universal kernel function PUK that has the advantage of a strong mapping power, simplified model building process and is computationally efficient. The mathematical formula for SVM is dependent on the type of data being processed. If the input data is linearly separated then hard-margin SVM is used however, in non-linear data case it will be soft-margin SVM. The hard-margin SVM formula is as given below in Eqn. (2)

$$f(x) = w^T x + b \quad (2)$$

The decision rule is $\hat{y} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } f(x) \geq 0 \\ -1 & \text{if } f(x) < 0 \end{cases}$

The optimization problem is defined as $\min_{w,b} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2$ subject to $y_i(w^T x_i + b) \geq 1$ for all values of $i=1$ to n . The soft-margin SVM formula is as given below in Eqn. (3)

$$\min_{w,b,\varepsilon} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^n \varepsilon_i \quad (3)$$

subject to $y_i(w^T x_i + b) \geq 1 - \varepsilon_i$, for all values of $i=1$ to n and $\varepsilon_i \geq 0$

For non-linearly separable data, SVM offers a kernel function to map data into a high-dimensional space where a linear boundary exists.

3.3.3 Naïve Bayes

It is a probabilistic classifier and a supervised machine-learning algorithm that implements Bayes theorem requiring no training time. It functions with an assumption that in a class all the features are mutually independent. Naïve Bayes classifiers are highly scalable, which enables the number of attributes in a learning problem to be symmetrical to various parameters. It is popular for text classification and processing such as spam detection. It also finds applications in automated medical diagnostics. In [9], authors have applied Naïve Bayes classification algorithm to build a predictive analytics model to predict salesperson performance. The mathematical formula for NB Classifiers is as described in Eqn. (4).

$$y = \arg \max_y P(y) \cdot \prod_{i=1}^n P(x_i|y) \quad (4)$$

Where, 'y' is the class label and $x = (x_1 \text{ to } x_n)$ is the feature vector.

3.3.4 Quadratic Discriminant Analysis

QDA is a classification technique that generalizes. In [16] authors implemented linear QDA to detect heart disease. The mathematical formula for QDA is derived from Bayes' theorem, used to determine probability whether an observation belongs to a class. It is an extension of linear discriminant analysis, which is used when a response variable can have more than two possible classes. The algorithm functions with the assumption that the observations from each class are normally distributed and that each class has its own covariance matrix [44]. QDA performs better when the training data is large, and the classes do not share a common covariance matrix. Eqn.(5) below provides the formula used for QDA.

$$\delta_k(x) = \log \pi_k - \frac{1}{2} (x - \mu_k)^T \Sigma_k^{-1} (x - \mu_k) - \frac{1}{2} \log |\Sigma_k| \quad (5)$$

$\delta_k(x)$ is the discriminant score for class 'k' and observation x - input vector, π_k - prior probability class of 'k', μ_k - mean vector for class 'k', Σ_k - covariance matrix for class 'k'.

3.3.5 Tools and Libraries

Experiments are conducted in Python programming environment. Libraries like numpy and pandas are used data cleansing and preparation. For model development and evaluation scikit-learn libraries are used. For visualization, matplotlib is implemented.

IV. EXPERIMENT RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The implementation results of proposed predictive algorithms performance are validated with scientific metrics. For better understanding along with the algorithms in the proposed methodology additional models such as KNN, DT, RF, GB, MLP, Ada Boost are also implemented. QDA algorithm demonstrated performance across two metrics achieving an accuracy of 90% and ROC of 93% indicating as a best model, while other models resulted performance any one the metric. Figure 3 below shows the graphical comparison key performance metrics achieved by different machine learning algorithms.

Figure 3. Prediction Classifiers Performance Comparison

4.1 Accuracy

Effectiveness of the model was vital to determine the accuracy of the results it generates. The accuracy is calculated as a ratio of true predictions to all the predictions. It is computed with the formula shown in Eqn. (6).

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \tag{6}$$

Where *TP* is confirmed positive, *TN* is confirmed negative, *FN* is unconfirmed negative, *FP* is unconfirmed positive.

Figure 4. Accuracy Comparison

The accuracy results generated by each of the implemented models in processing the dataset is compared as shown in Figure 4. The SVM model attained 92% accuracy followed by QDA with 90%, LR – 88% and Naïve Bayes – 82%. A high accuracy indicates that the model correctly predicts a large proportion of instances.

4.2 Precision

The correctness of the positive outcomes of a model is crucial for its reliability. In other words, of all the positive samples generated by the model, what part of them are truly positive. It helps to eliminate the chance of false alarms creating trust on the positive prediction. These metrics establish the correctness of prediction by considering the inaccurately classified sample. The formula used to calculate it is as shown in Eqn. (7).

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (7)$$

The results from the algorithms compared are as shown in Figure 5 below. The QDA model produced 74% precision, while LR, SVM, and NB scored 67, 0 and 64 respectively. A high precision means the model is good at avoiding false positives, i.e., it rarely mislabels a negative instance as positive.

Figure 5. Precision Comparison

4.3 Recall

Recall metric also known as sensitivity score signifies of all actual positive samples, how many are truly positive. It works best with imbalanced datasets. The below Eqn. (8). shows how the recall of a system is calculated.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (8)$$

Below Figure 6 shows the comparison of the recall metrics from various algorithms considered in the methodology. QDA model got a score of 54% whereas NB got 51%, LR got 34% and SVM scored 0%. A high score of recall indicates that the model is good at identifying most positives correctly.

Figure 6. Recall Comparison

4.4 F1 Score

This metric is primarily a balance of both precision and recall, calculated as a harmonic mean of both. It is mainly used to deal with imbalanced datasets. The formula to calculate F1 score as given below in Eqn. (9).

$$F1 = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (9)$$

The results of F1 score are as shown in Figure 7, below. The QDA model attained 47% score, whereas NB, LR and SVM got 38%, 34% and 0% respectively. A high F1 score indicates a good balance between avoiding false positives (precision) and capturing the true positives (recall)

Figure 7. F1 Score Comparison

4.5 ROC AUC

Receiver Operating Characteristic - Area Under the Curve (ROC-AUC) evaluates the quality of binary classification. It measures how well the model distinguishes positive and negative classes. It is best suited for both balanced and imbalanced datasets. ROC Curve is a graph plot of True Positive Rate (TPR) on Y axis and False Positive Rate (FPR) on X-axis. A curve closer to the top left corner is considered a better model. AUC is the area under that curve with value between 0.9 -1.0 indicating an excellent model; 0.8-0.9, a good model; 0.6-0.7 a moderate model; 0.5 or lesser is like random guessing and flawed model. The comparison is shown in Figure 8 below.

Figure 8. ROC-AUC Comparison

4.5 Discussion

The main goal of implementing the predictive models is to identify the best model to predict whether a customer will make a term deposit. The visual comparison of ROC-AUC score for all the algorithms implemented for comparison this study is as shown in Figure 9 below. Based on the scores the algorithms can be further tiered down, which clearly indicates the QDA outperformed all the models with ROC-AUC results.

- AUC > 0.9: QDA, Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression; AUC = 0.7 – 0.8: MLP Classifier, Ada Boost, KNN
- AUC = 0.6 – 0.7: Gradient Boosting; AUC ≤ 0.5: Random Forest, SVM, Decision Tree

Figure 9. ROC-AUC Results

V.CONCLUSION

This document discussed the performance of predictive models using supervised machine learning on a real-world direct marketing multivariate dataset. Research work of various authors is studied through documenting future scope and further extension. Along with the four important algorithms in predictive analytics, additional models are also implemented, and a comparative analysis using scientific methods are presented with performance metrics. From the results it is concluded that QDA model outperformed in accuracy and ROC AUC score over other algorithms. Predictive Analytics using QDA can be further explored for different real world multi-class or multi-label classification scenarios. Another important scope for future research is to try an ensemble of the best performing predictive algorithms as it is quickly emerging as the new future trend.

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